

HOW MANY WORDS ARE REALLY NEED TO COMMUNICATE IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: The article explores how important to learn by heart so many words in English to communicate with. Explains which words are commonly used among English speakers

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To work out how many words we need to know to be able to speak a second language I decided to look into how many words we know in English. Today a lot of people are trying to learn English since it is necessary to find a well-paid, appropriate job for future career. Henceforth, English learners want to communicate in English but they often have some difficulties to speak up because of lack of word building or vocabulary. So why they all are made to learn by heart so many words even though they will never use in their jobs. According to the statistics there are over 170000 unique words in the English language. And the number is still growing day by day. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, not to mention 47156 are obsolete words. To quote a well-known internet meme "ain't nobody got time for that". What we needed was a mathematical cheat. Fortunately for us somebody beat us to it. Linguists Paul Nation and John Read along with their colleague Robin Goulden, came up with a test involving only 50 words. Their theory is that if you count up how many of the 50 words you understand and multiply the total by 500 you are able to estimate your total English vocabulary. Words start of simply enough; dog, editor, immense, but they quickly become more obscure, for example would you know how to use "oleaginous" or "cowsucker" in a sentence?

So how many words do we know? Stuart Webb, professor of applied linguistics at the University of Western Ontario, has studied the process of learning vocabulary. He discovered that it is incredibly difficult for a language learner to ever know as many words as a native speaker. Typically native speakers know 15000 to 20000 words families or lemmas in their first languages. Word family/ lemma is a root word and all its inflections, for example: run, running, ran. So does someone who can hold a decent conversation in a second language know 15000 to 20000 words? Is this a realistic goal for our English learners. Prof

Webb found that people who have been studying languages in a traditional setting- say French in Britain or English in Japan- often struggle to learn more than 2000 to 3000 words, even after years of study.

In fact, a study in Taiwan showed that after nine years of learning a foreign language half of the students failed to learn the most frequently-used 1000 words. You don't need to know all of the words in a language. So which words should we learn? Prof Webb says the most effective way to be able to speak a language quickly is to pick the 800 to 1000 lemmas which appear most frequently in a language, and learn those. If you learn only 800 of the most frequently-used lemmas in English, you will be able to understand 75% of the language as it is spoken in normal life. These 800 lemmas are a lot more valuable than other words, simply because they are used far more often. For example it is much more useful to know the word "house" than the word "abode", and you will get fewer odd looks if you say "perhaps" rather than "peradventure".

Here I try to elucidate the most common words by dividing them into categories; noun, verb, pronoun, adjective, adverb, auxiliary verb.

Verb: Actually in every language every sentence requires the use of a verb. We use verbs to represent actions, feelings and states of being. When learning English, it is easy to use the same verbs repeatedly. So, in addition to teaching you some of the most commonly used verbs, you will also be given synonyms to help add some variety to your conversations and writing. Here are some examples of them;

Come – (syn) appear, arrive, occur – e.g Can you come to my house tonight

Find -- (syn) discover, identify, locate – e.g I can't find my suitcase

Give – (syn) allow, award, grant – e.g Can you give a minute, please?

Get – (syn) gain, obtain, earn – e.g I hope I get a raise this month

Go – (syn) flee, depart, progress – e.g Sam, go and speak with your father!

Have – (syn) acquire, accept, possess – e.g I have the forms in my bag

Know – (syn) perceive, realize, notice – e.g I know this can't be easy to say

Look – (syn) glance, peer, stare – e.g They will look at the sculpture

Make – (syn) compose, generate, produce –e.g What are you making for the picnic

Say– (syn) announce, convey, express – e.g Don't say things you don't mean!

See – (syn) detect, notice, view – e.g I could see she was angry from her manner

Auxiliary verbs: They are extremely useful in English. Therefore they are referred to as "helping or modal verbs". Auxiliary verbs help to form certain

verbs tenses, voice and moods. Needless to say, we often use them quite often.

For example:

Be – I will be swimming tomorrow morning

Can – Can you pass the salt, please!

Do – Do they always come this late?

Shall – I shall ask him tomorrow and etc

Nouns: It is a word that refers to a place, a person, a thing, a quantity, an activity.

You cannot have a sentence without the use of some sort of noun.

Here some more examples for most common nouns:

Man – The man sat quietly on the sofa.

Day – It was the last day of summer.

Thing – We have both brought the same thing.

Year – This year has been one of the craziest yet!

Woman – He saw the woman from the across the room.

Pronouns: It is used to substitute a noun or a noun phrase in a sentence. We can only use a pronoun if the noun or noun phrase has been referred to previously.

He – This is my brother David. He likes to go out ice skating.

Her – Her shoes were left out in the rain all night.

Them – I went with them to see the play and so on.

Adjectives: They add detail to your speaking and writing. They are used to describe nouns and they provide the reader or listener with additional information. If you want to liven up your conversations, adjectives are the way to go!

All – Did you put all of the food away?

Different – Can you get me a different mug?

White -- When I opened my eyes, I saw white walls.

New – Her new shoes are black.

Adverbs: They are brilliant words that help you describe a verb, an adjective, another adverb or entire sentences. You may have learned that most adverbs end in -ly, this may be true, but the most common adverbs may surprise you.

Also – We also live up the hill!

Now – Are you ready to go now?

Then – We cannot go back to how it was then.

Very – Diego was very angry after the meeting. and so on.

So if you want to communicate with native speaker as like as him or her, you should not learn all the words exist in the language but try to learn and use some of them which are most common used. Addition to the idea of some professors

the estimate number of words we should learn to communicate is 8000 words. Actually some specialist say that 800 words are enough but according to Wikipedia and source of language works written by experts the number is 8000 and it is said that not try to learn more to make a conversation with native speaker or in other conditions. It is crucial to concentrate on the limit of the words needed to communicate and use them in active by speaking or writing processes.

Bibliography:

1. Measuring Native-Speaker Vocabulary Size I.S.P. Nation Victoria University of Wellington Averil Coxhead Victoria University of Wellington 2021
2. Essentials of Teaching Academic Vocabulary Part of the Cengage Learning for Academic Success Series) by Cynthia Schuemann, Joy Reid, Patricia Byrd, Averil Coxhead 2005 Format:Paperback Language:English ISBN:0618230149 ISBN13:9780618230143 Release Date:July 2005 Publisher:CENGAGE Learning
3. Webb, Stephen A.; Gray, Mel; Plath, Debbie (2009). Evidence-based social work: a critical stance. London New York: Routledge. ISBN 9780415468237.
4. Webb, Stephen A.; Harlow, Elizabeth, eds. (2003). Information and communication technologies in the welfare services. London Philadelphia, Pennsylvania: Jessica Kingsley Publishers. ISBN 9781843100492.
5. Wodak, Ruth, & Forchtner, Bernhard (Eds.) (2017). The Routledge Handbook of Language and Politics. London: Routledge.

